

OPPOSITIONS OF TOPONYMS IN ANTIPHRASES

OPOSICIONES DE LOS TOPONIMOS EN ANTÍFRASIS

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Resumen

El objetivo de la investigación fue identificar los medios para implementar el principio de contraste en antífrasis con un topónimo como componente clave. El método fue analítico y análisis linguacultural. Nuestro hallazgo muestra que los enigmas - antífrases se crean al transformar unidades precedentes; diferentes tipos de unidades precedentes, que tienen un profundo potencial lingüístico, y que se utilizan prototipos; el cifrado del texto de origen se basa en el principio del contraste. Este trabajo distingue tipos especiales de sustituciones de contraste: oposiciones basadas en características de objetos geográficos; Sustituciones de topónimos con un elemento nominal.

Palabras clave: topónimo, antífrase, contraste, oposición.

ABSTRACT

The aim of the research was to identify the means of implementing the principle of contrast in antiphraasis with a toponym as a key component. The method was analytical and linguacultural analysis. Our finding shows that riddles - antiphraases are created by transforming precedent units; different types of precedent units, which have a deep linguacultural potential, and are used as prototypes (8-9) the encryption of the source text is based on the principle of contrast. This work distinguishes special types of contrast substitutions: oppositions based on features of geographic objects; replacements of toponyms with a nominal element.

Keywords: toponym, antiphraasis, contrast, opposition.

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INTRODUCTION

Whenever we express the word or the term in a way which in addition to the literal meaning, has a hidden implied meaning, and our purpose is exactly to convey this second virtual (hidden) meaning, we have used innuendo. Most writers distinguish between sarcasm and innuendo. However, some believe that sometimes or most of the time, sarcasm includes innuendo as well. Critical and unfriendly statements may be uttered with purpose of smutting, such as saying "do not work too hard" to a lazy person. The use of smut adds some kind of humor to the statement and makes the critique politer and less aggressive. Sarcasm may be neglected in the form of writing, because most of the time, change of the tone and song of the sentence is needed to express it. Understanding the elegance of the use of language requires a second-degree interpretation of the speaker's intentions; different parts of the brain must work together to understand the meaning behind sarcasm. This complexity, makes it difficult for many who suffer from brain damage, such as forgetfulness and autism to understand sarcasm (albeit not always).

This article studies the linguacultural understanding of oppositional relations in toponyms within antifrasis (8-9) the essence of the antiphase game is the following: Some Runet users replace all the components of a precedent prototype with the words of opposite meaning so that other participants of the game would guess initial phrases or texts.

The analysis of game transforms is relevant because precedent units, prototypes of antifrasis, are closely related to collective representations invariant to national culture. Being part of background knowledge, they ensure mutual understanding of the members of a language community. In modern linguistics, many researchers are interested in Analyzing the relevance of precedent phenomena and archetypes for modern linguistic consciousness (Kulkova, Fattakhova and Zinecker, 2015).

The fact that precedent units may comprise words that cannot have antonyms in their composition makes antifrasis very promising for analyzing the linguistic-cognitive principle of contrast.

Geographical vocabulary is known as a special type of proper names, meaning the name of any geographical object and having no antonyms, which is significant for identifying the means of implementing contrast in antifrasis with a toponym component. In our card file, we have 114 antifrasis with a toponym component. Geographical names have a long history of analysis; their formation and development are largely determined by social, historical, national and cultural factors: "Geographical names appeared at the earliest stage of the society development because of the need to name surrounding objects, landscapes, and lands in the process of their cognition by man" (Superanskaya, 1987, p. 182). In this regard, antifrasis with a toponym as their key component are a novel material

for investigating verbal interrelations between proper names in terms of cultural linguistics.

It should be noted that any language game is a certain type of speech behavior, based on deliberate (conscious, thoughtful) violation of systemic relations in language. In antifrasis, substitutions of words are not just deliberate distortions of the form of precedent units in order to create a language game, but also an expression of a new denotative or connotative meaning.

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this analysis is to explore the means of implementing the principle of contrast in antifrasis with a toponym as a key component.

For this purpose, we used a combination of the following methods:

Semantic methods, stylistic method, descriptive methods and analytical method, also the methods of component, contextual, cognitive and linguacultural analysis.

RESULTS

Various precedent units act as prototypes of antiphrases with a toponym as a key component:

a) Premia (proverbs, sayings): *Your nose will lead you out of **Moscow** (Your tongue will lead you to **Kiev**); **Carthage** instantly collapsed (**Moscow** was not immediately built);*

b) The names of literary works and citations from them: *The Federation of the **NKVD** (the Republic of **ShKID**); An exile from **Paris** to **Courchevel** (A Journey from **St. Petersburg** to **Moscow**);*

c) The titles and texts of musical works: ***Baikal** Morning (**Moscow** Nights); For a month, till the third, I'm going to **Shmelevo** (I'm going to **Komarovo** for a week, till the second);*

d) The names of the movies (performances, plays, etc.) and the words of the characters: *In **Tehran**, everything is restless (Everything is calm in **Baghdad**); Nobody seems to be willing to go to **Tashkent**, as if it were made of silicone (Everyone seems to be willing to squeeze into **Moscow**, as if it were made of rubber), etc.*

As we know, toponyms can be divided into two groups:

Unlike ordinary objects, geographical objects get names of two types: general, introducing them into a system of certain concepts (mountain, river, city) and individual ones, which cannot be transferred from one object to another (Ermolovich, 2001). Most of the toponyms in antifrasis are individual, the meaning of which consists of “a certain minimum set of the most significant features of the geographical object”. *Korea has nothing (Greece has everything); Here comes winter, hello, Norway (That's the end of the summer, goodbye, Italy)*, etc.

According to our observations, when creating antifrasis, users gravitate to symmetric (soponymic) toponym changes, for example, country-country: *Germany-Brazil: Zero to Five (Argentina-Jamaica: Five to Zero)*; city – city: *Karaganda trusts smile (Moscow does not trust tears)*; river - river: *An elderly Georgian is working beyond the Volga (A young Cossack is walking about the Don)*; *Any fish will reach the other bank of the Moskva Rive (A rare bird will reach the middle of the Dnieper)*; island-island: *For two nights snow has not been moving near Sakhalin (For four days the blizzard has been swaying over Dixon)*.

Nevertheless, asymmetric replacements of place names also occur, for example, lake – river: *Nearby, Lake Baikal is withering slowly (From afar, the Volga River flows a long way)*; island (islands) - country: *The beast, hating Somalia (The man, loving Sakhalin)*; *Ordinary weekdays of Argentineans in Hawaii (Incredible adventures of Italians in Russia)*.

We have observed that the antiphraic corpus rarely contains cases when contrast associated toponyms are based on linguistic mechanisms of expressing contrast (antonym, hyponymy, heterogeneous oppositions, etc.).

CIRCLE OF NAMES

The reasons for this are obvious: this kind of association is possible only in a circle of names with a living internal form. Thus, in compound words and composite toponyms, one of the components may have an antonym (white-black) in its usage, which stimulates toponymic associations: *Your old age, Montenegro (My youth, Byelorussia)*; *The White River and a beautiful Zhiguli (The Black Sea and a white Mercedes)*.

WAY OF CREATING CONTRAST

A specific way of creating contrast, which can be attributed to linguistic means, is a permutation of letters based on “reading from the right to the left” (according to the rules of Russian writing, the words are read from left to right): *The Mainland of GALUG (The GULAG Archipelago)*.

Much more frequently the contrast of proper names is based on cultural associations: geographical knowledge, folklore and literary texts, “eternal images”,

historical events, cultural traditions, etc. Firstly, almost all toponyms are closely related to the essential characteristics of the geographical object, for example Kilimanjaro – “The highest and potentially active stratovolcano of Africa, located in the north-east of Tanzania, the highest point of the continent”; Antarctica – “The continent, located in the extreme south of Earth”. As D. I. Ermolovich (2001) noted, “geographical information is contained in these names for the entire language community, it is coded at the level of the language-system” (Ermolovich, 2011, p.200).

Therefore, in antiphrases, the contrast substitution of a toponym can be created in accordance with specific features of a geographical object:

- a) Geographical location (north-south, east-west): *If I forgot to collect my change - I would die in **Kolyma** (If I knew the talon- I would live in **Sochi**);*
- b) The relief of the place (the highest peak - the deepest depression): *The white devil dies in the **Mariana Trench** (The black goddess lives on **Kilimanjaro**);*
- c) Climatic differences (cold - hot): ***Antarctica**, Antarctica ... There you are also badly starved (**Haiti**, Haiti ... Here we are also well fed), etc.*

It should be noted that objective geographical features are often complicated by cultural associations.

PAI ACCUMULLATES

Thus, Kolyma-Sochi pair accumulates not only north-south and cold-heat oppositions, but also the knowledge that one of the places is the location of prison camps, and the other is a well-known resort town. Similarly, the East-West dichotomy is a concept more geographic than sociological and cultural, it shows the differences between two different civilizations; as a means of creating antifrasis, the East-West opposition continues the tradition of opposing two types of cultures: *Relax! America will not remember us! The **East** will do you harm (Be strong, Russia will not forget you, the **West** will help us); The **West** is a thick thing, Makarych (The **East** is a delicate matter, Petrukha), etc.*

The analysis of our card file of antifrasis shows that in most cases the opposition of toponyms is based on the archetypical opposition “us - them”, which “permeates the whole culture and is one of the main concepts of any communal, mass, national, folk worldview” (Stepanova, 2004, p.922): *An elderly burgher is not riding about the **Rhine** (A young Cossack is walking about the **Don**); Sleepyheads in **Kazan** (Sleepless in **Seattle**). In these and many other cases, users replace Russia's geographical nominations for place names that refer to geographical objects of other countries.*

THE OPPOSITION

The opposition “us - them”, reflecting the initial comprehension of the spatial model of the world, has long penetrated into different spheres of human existence. “Every culture begins with the division of the world into its internal (“us”) space and external (“them”) ... the internal space is defined as our own, cultural, safe, harmoniously organized, etc. It is confronted by them-space, alien, hostile, dangerous, and chaotic” (Lottman, 1996, p.175) It is clear that the dichotomy “us - them” is often complicated by the opposition “friend or foe”, conditioned both by cultural factors and mutual historical relations between countries, which is used to create antifrasis . In the following examples, the choice of a contrast associate reflects the military confrontation between Russia and Germany, the political polarity of America and the USSR during the Cold War, the political opposition of the Soviet Union and Israel, etc.: *Who dies in **Germany** badly (Who lives in **Russia** well); Your index is the **USA** (My address is the **Soviet Union**); Hello, **Israel**, fresh from the bath (Farewell, unwashed **Russia**).*

It is obvious that the opposition of toponyms, created on the basis of the oldest dichotomy “us - them”, synthesizes various associations, for example, *Russia-Guadeloupe / Hawaii* binomes can be interpreted as oppositions not only along the line “us - them”, but also according to the geographical distance of objects, their climatic differences, their common and exotic features: *The lifestyle of Russians in **Guadeloupe** / Ordinary weekdays of Argentineans in **Hawaii** (Incredible adventures of Italians in **Russia**).*

It should be noted that the opposition “our space – their space” has a “center - periphery” option. “In ancient concepts, our own and their space are thought of as a set of concentric circles: in the very center is a person and his/her immediate environment, and the degree of space alienation increases with a distance from the center” (Zakharenko, 2013), therefore, the name of the country’s capital as a political and cultural center is often replaced by the nomination of a non-capital city and vice versa: *In the village of **Moscow**, days are bright (In the city of **Sochi**, nights are dark); To go to **Moscow** with an alien pot (To go to **Tula** with your own samovar), etc.*

If we discuss, which toponyms are most frequently subjected to contrast substitutions when creating antifrasis , they are Russia / Rus nominations, on the one hand, and America on the other.

The reasons for the fact that the names Russia, Rus are first in the range of geographical names subjected to reflection are obvious - as they say, “Self comes first”: *In **America** there is a reviva (In **Russia** there is no sex); How disgusting are mornings in **Germany** (How delightful are evenings in **Russia**); Hello, clean **China** (Goodbye, unwashed **Russia**), etc.* Unlike Russia, the toponym America,

frequently used in antifrasis , is found in transformation-riddles, not in prototypes. At the same time, the material of antifrasis testifies both to the relevance of the eponymous concept in the modern linguistic consciousness, and to the presence of the notions of America's opposition to the rest of the world in the minds of the Russians.

This can explain why this name is chosen by users, when it is necessary to encrypt not only the word Russia in antifrasis , but also the names of such parts of the world as Africa and Europe (although, as participants in the game note, the opposition *Europe-Asia* would be more logical): *Adults, crawl out to fly from **America** (Children, do not go to walk in **Africa!**); The body is lying in **America** (The ghost is wandering around **Europe**).*

SYNONYMOUS SERIES OF ANTIFRASIS

In previous studies, a thesis was put forward that if synonymous series of antiphrasal riddles have the same prototype, it testifies not only to the relevance of the original precedent phenomenon for modern society, but also to the importance of certain concepts that arouse various mental associations in users.

VARIANTS OF LINGUACULTURAL ASSOCIATIONS

Various variants of linguacultural associations caused by toponyms can be exemplified by the synonymous series of transformations with Zakharenko (2013, P18) well-known lines “Say, uncle, it's not for nothing, that Moscow, burnt by fire, was given to Frenchmen?”:

a) Associations based on historical facts and socio-geographical analogies – it was a war with the French, therefore, the capital of Russia is contrasted with the capital of France: *Keep mum, auntie, it's not for money, that the flooded **Paris** was taken from Russians;*

b) Associations reflecting the idea of competition between the two Russian capitals (a kind of cultural stereotype), complicated by the antonymy *fire - flood*, and the knowledge that there are frequent floods in St. Petersburg / Leningrad (cf.: “The Copper Horseman” by Pushkin (cited in Foxcroft, 2015): *Keep mum, aunt, that for free **Leningrad**, washed away with water, was taken from Italians;*

c) The antithesis “capital” – “provincial town”: *Silence, aunt, for nothing, the flooded **Bobruisk** was not given to Englishmen!* (Compare the opposition with the nominal name: *Close your ears, aunt, though for nothing, the **province**, reborn by the flood, was not taken from Chukchi).*

DISCUSSION

Summarizing the above, we arrive at the following conclusions: riddles - antifrasis are created by transforming precedent units; different types of precedent units, which have a deep linguacultural potential, are used as prototypes; the encryption of the source text is based on the principle of contrast; in antifrasis, contrasting substitutions used to create toponymic opposites are based on the ancient dichotomy of “us – them”, which correlates with the following oppositions: *our space - their space; center - periphery; friend - foe; east - west*. In antifrasis, the contrast of toponyms is predominantly symmetrical (such as city-city), asymmetric substitutions are rare.

This work distinguishes special types of contrast substitutions: oppositions based on features of geographic objects; replacements of toponyms with a nominal element by preserving their word-formation structure with the replacement of its morphemes, or all its constituent elements with contrasting ones.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, toponyms arouse different associations in people due to their history and national culture.

Antifrasis with a toponymic component represent new material for the analysis of verbal paradigmatic relations in terms of cultural linguistics, while by clarifying the types of contrasting toponym substitutions, we learn what constants of Russian linguacultural preserve their relevance for the consciousness of modern native speakers.

Transformations of well-known sayings with the purpose of creating riddles updates the old words of wisdom in the linguistic consciousness of new generations; antifrasis - “flip-flops”, do not simply distort certain phrases, but play with their form attempting to rethink traditional authoritative knowledge in a new way.

Thus, the precedent unit develops, is enriched with new semantics, in other words, continues to live and fulfill a social function, preserving a single fund of knowledge in the linguacultural community.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors assert that represented data do not contain conflict of interests.

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